

Outcrossed seeds collected on male sterile plants of the initial population were bulked to form the next population, CNA-IRAT 5/0/1. The procedure was repeated three times to obtain the CNA-IRAT 5/0/3 population.

Samples of bulk seeds harvested on self-pollinated plants of the CNA-IRAT 5/0/2 population are available to rice breeders. □

Some Indonesian restorers and maintainers of WA cyto sterile lines

B. Sutaryo, Plant Breeding Division, Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops, Subang, Indonesia

We crossed Chinese CMS line V20 A as the female parent with 10 standard rice cultivars during 1987-88 wet season. Hybrids and the male parents grown in the test cross nursery in 1988 dry season were examined (12 plants each) for pollen and spikelet fertility. Male parents of the F₁ that showed 71-90% pollen fertility and higher than 80% spikelet fertility were designated restorers. Male parents showing 5-9%

Spikelet and pollen fertility percentages in F₁ hybrids and their male parents.

Cross and male parent	Pollen fertility (%)	Spikelet fertility (%)
V20 A/Bahbolon	79	83.2
Bahbolon	82	88.6
V20 A/Cimanuk	78	81.3
Cimanuk	83	82.5
V20 A/Batang Pane	79	83.0
Batang Pane	81	90.5
V20 A/Citanduy	77	80.0
Citanduy	80	82.9
V20 A/Ciliwung	83	84.2
Ciliwung	90	91.0
V20 A/Bogowonto	82	86.5
Bogowonto	90	92.5
V20 A/Bahbutong	6	10.5
Bahbutong	77	88.2
V20 A/Adil	5	11.5
Adil	76	86.1
V20 A/Cisokan	9	10.0
Cisokan	79	85.5
V20 A/S397b-40-2	7	12.8
S397b-40-2	75	83.0

pollen fertility were designated prospective maintainers.

Bahbolon, Cimanuk, Batang Pane, Citanduy, Ciliwung, and Bogowonto were identified as restorers; Bahbutong,

Adil, Cisokan, and S397b-40-2 as prospective maintainers (see table). The prospective maintainers need to be tested by recurrent backcrossing. □

Yield of F₁ hybrids at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI), Aduthurai, India

V. Sivasubramanian, S. Ganapathy, A. P. M. K. Soundararaj, and N. Nadarajan, TRRI, Aduthurai 612101, India

We evaluated 22 F₁ hybrids developed at IRRRI and 2 hybrids developed at

TRRI 1986-88. Single seedlings were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing in 3 × 2-m plots with 3 replications. Plots were fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Many hybrids yielded less than local check ADT36. Eleven hybrids had 12 to 78% standard heterosis. The most promising were IR54752 A/IR25912-81-2-1 R and V20 A/T1154 (see table). □

Duration, grain yield, and standard heterosis of F₁ hybrids at Aduthurai, India, 1986-88.

Hybrid or check	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>1986</i>			
ADT36 (check)	110	8.4	
IR46828 A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	120	9.4	12
ZS97 A/Milyang 54	135	7.3	-12
IR46830 A/IR13292-5-3	113	6.5	-22
IR54752 A/IR54 R	129	4.5	-46
IR54752 A/IR19392-211-1	130	4.2	-50
IR54752 A/IR4422-480-2-3-3	130	4.2	-50
IR54752 A/IR20933-68-21	131	3.4	-60
IR54752 A/IR14753-120-3	131	3.1	-63
LSD (P = 0.05)	-	0.9	
<i>1987</i>			
ADT36 (check)	108	6.3	
IR54752 A/IR25912-81-2-1 R	117	11.3	78
IR54752 A/IR19392-211-1 R	119	8.9	41
IR54752 A/IR28178-70-2-3 R	121	8.8	38
IR54752 A/IR19058-107-1 R	107	7.5	19
IR54752 A/IR28912-63-2-2 R	118	7.4	17
IR54752 A/IR46 R	118	7.3	14
IR54752 A/IR64 R	124	7.2	14
IR54752 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	113	7.2	14
IR54752 A/IR13419-113-1 R	131	5.3	-17
IR46830 A/IR9761-19-1 R	103	4.4	-30
IR54752 A/IR21916-128-2-2-3 R	125	4.2	-34
LSD (P = 0.05)	-	0.7	
<i>1988</i>			
ADT36 (check)	107	4.8	
Co 43 (check)	127	6.5	
V20 A/T1154 (ADH2)	108	7.4	57
IR54752 A/IR46 R	123	6.7	3
V20 A/IR18349-22-1-2-1-1 (ADH1)	110	3.9	-18
IR54752 A/ARC11353 R	122	2.5	-61
IR54752 A/IR54 R	128	1.6	-15
LSD (P = 0.05)	-	1.4	

The International Rice Research Newsletter is mailed free to individuals and institutions engaged in rice research and training. For further information, write IRRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.